

THE FABRICATION OF BORON FIBER
REINFORCED ALUMINUM MATRIX
COMPOSITES

Karl M. Prewé
United Aircraft Research Laboratories
East Hartford, Connecticut

The prominence of boron aluminum in current and future aerospace design concepts is due to not only outstanding mechanical and physical properties, but also the relative ease with which large and complex components can be fabricated. The purpose of this paper is to summarize the requirements needed to fabricate high performance boron aluminum composites and to present a new fabrication procedure. This process will be shown to provide the capability for the production of fully densified high strength boron aluminum composite components in a total process time of less than ten minutes. The process can be performed in air, thus providing the basis for low cost component fabrication.

Introduction

Metal matrix composites are currently being considered for aerospace applications because of the superior values of specific stiffness and specific strength they can provide. Despite these, and other well-documented advantages in mechanical properties, material applications have been slow to develop due to the increased cost of using composites. This increased cost has frequently been discussed in terms of the basic materials costs, particularly fiber cost. However, overall fabrication costs also contribute significantly to the final cost to the user. As an example, at the time of this report the cost of fully consolidated boron-aluminum panels containing 50 percent boron by weight can exceed \$200 per pound while the cost of the boron fiber is below \$200 per pound.

The high fabrication cost of boron-aluminum hardware can be related to the time and atmospheric constraints currently imposed on diffusion bonding procedures. The need for a vacuum or inert atmosphere has caused the use of elaborate bagging procedures or the construction of large atmospheric chambers at considerable cost in both labor and equipment. Similarly, the use of long hot pressing cycles with associated massive heated dies and tooling have also added considerable expense. Fabrication time cycles of over several hours duration have been common. Typical bonding conditions are given in Table I for both green (organic binder) and plasma sprayed tape precursors.

In the following report a brief discussion of the process requirements for the successful bonding of boron aluminum composites will be presented. This will be followed by a description of a recently developed process (Quick Bonding) for the low cost fabrication of boron aluminum components which demonstrated that composite bonding times of as short as five minutes can provide high strength material and that bonding can be performed in air without the imposition of any performance penalty. The key to the successful achievement of these advances has been the utilization of plasma sprayed tapes.

Boron Aluminum Bonding

The procedures currently being utilized for the diffusion bonding of boron aluminum are remarkably similar to those developed in the late 1960's. In general, the adequacy of a bonding procedure

has been judged by the levels of composite axial and transverse tensile strength obtained. Several aspects of composite bonding are discussed below.

Fiber-Matrix Bonding

The nature of the fiber matrix bond is extremely important in determining overall composite behavior. A bonding procedure which results in an inadequate bond will result in composites having low transverse strength, low axial strength (sometimes) and inferior environmental stability. The other extreme of bonding can cause extensive reaction between fiber and matrix forming sufficient AlB_2 to cause fiber strength degradation.

The three major ways in which boron fiber strength can be degraded during composite fabrication are: formation of boron oxide, formation of aluminum diboride and mechanical breakage. The last of these is a major problem, particularly in multi-axial arrays and in the fabrication of complex shapes where considerable motion of composite material occurs during consolidation. The two fiber-matrix reaction problems are minimized by control of the atmosphere, temperature and time of pressure application. It is extremely difficult to provide a complete description of the reaction mechanisms which lead to degradation. The first step in the formation of the aluminum diboride product must entail breakage of the aluminum oxide on the aluminum matrix foils or powder. Once this has occurred, then the aluminum-boron reaction can proceed. Thus, general guidelines to avoid fiber degradation by this reaction must take into account the amount of Al_2O_3 initially present on the matrix surface, the extent and time (with respect to thermal history) of pressure application, and the complete thermal cycle. Several research programs have demonstrated the rate of fiber degradation as a result of composite thermal exposure (10,11), however, data obtained from long term annealing and tensile testing of previously fabricated composites can only partially serve as a guide for fabrication conditions.

The use of silicon carbide and nitride coatings on boron fibers decreases the severity of the reaction problem and may, in the future provide the most reliable way of fabricating boron-aluminum composites by eliminating the high level of concern for complete composite thermal and deformation history.

Matrix-Matrix Bonding

Because boron-aluminum composites are fabricated from an assembly of precursor tapes, the extent of matrix-matrix bonding achieved is also of concern. It is possible, through control of matrix bonding, to achieve a wide variety of composite properties. Figure 1 presents the microstructure of a well bonded composite diffusion bonded from an array of plasma sprayed tapes. Complete bonding and densification has resulted in high composite transverse and shear strengths. It should be noted that some "nesting" of the fibers takes place to form a hexagonal rather than square array so that there is little difference between matrix bonds within a given tape layer and between adjacent tapes. This is quite different from the microstructure of a composite fabricated from layers of fully consolidated tapes, Fig. 2. In this case there are distinct differences between tape-tape matrix bonding and internal tape bonding. Note also that there is no tendency for nesting of fibers. It is therefore difficult to achieve completely well bonded composites with fully preconsolidated tapes because of the difficulty of achieving sufficient aluminum deformation to break up the oxide layer between tapes. The degree of this inter-tape bonding is not always assessed in composite programs because the usual procedures of axial and transverse tensile testing are not very sensitive to this bond. As an example, one can consider the properties of resin bonded boron aluminum, Table II and Fig. 3 (12). In this case high axial and transverse composite strengths and moduli are achieved by just adhesively bonding together fully preconsolidated layers of boron aluminum tape. The low strength tape-tape bonds only effect the interlaminar shear properties measured.

The Quick Bond Process

Although the data in Table I indicate times at maximum temperature of approximately 30-60 minutes, total process times for boron aluminum are considerably longer. Total times in excess of 3 hours are typical due to slow heat up and cool down procedures and massive tooling utilized. These long times are a requirement of the apparatus used and not the composite bonding mechanism. The actual requirements for bonding consist of: (1) adequate deformation of the matrix to rupture the Al_2O_3 surfaces, (2) high enough temperature and long enough time to permit matrix deformation without fiber breakage, (3) high enough temperature and long enough time to form fiber-matrix and matrix-matrix bonds, (4) low enough temperature and short enough time after oxide breakup to prevent excessive fiber-

matrix reaction and, (5) sufficient protection of both matrix and fiber to prevent oxidation at high temperature. It will be shown in the following that all of these requirements can be met by conditions markedly dissimilar from those given in Table I. The data presented are only a small part of the total investigation performed to demonstrate the "Quick Bond" process (13).

Materials

Matrix - The composite matrix plays an important role in providing the composite with corrosion resistance, off-axis strength, impact resistance, plasticity and suitability for secondary bonding procedures. The 6061 aluminum matrix was chosen for this program because of its excellent combination of all of these properties. Because precursor tapes for this program are fabricated by the plasma spray process, the matrix alloy was obtained in both foil (25 μm and 50 μm thicknesses) and powder forms.

Fiber - The 145 μm diameter boron fiber was chosen because of its high strength in both the axial and transverse directions as well as its commercial availability. The fiber was purchased from the Hamilton Standard Division of United Aircraft Corporation with a minimum spool strength of $3.45 \times 10^9 \text{N/m}^2$.

Plasma Sprayed Tape

Unlike polystyrene bonded tapes, plasma sprayed tapes are held together with a well-bonded, porous aluminum layer (5). This layer bonds the boron fibers to the substrate foil and provides the following advantages.

- (a) The boron fibers are effectively encapsulated between the plasma sprayed powder and the substrate foil and thus protected from the environment. The pores of the plasma spray do not form a continuous network.
- (b) Bagging procedures or vacuum chambers are not required to provide a means for evacuating a fugitive organic binder.
- (c) An evacuation time at elevated temperature, or within a given temperature range, is not needed to facilitate organic removal prior to bonding.
- (d) The rearrangement of fibers during bonding is minimized due to the presence of the sprayed powder between and around each fiber.

(e) The porous nature of the plasma spray coating provides large amounts of local deformation and plasticity during composite bonding. This is of major importance because the diffusion bonding of aluminum first requires breakage of any oxide layer and this is achieved effectively by local metal plasticity.

The plasma spray process of boron fibers must be performed in inert atmosphere. This can be provided by a shroud gas or a closed chamber. If performed in air, the fiber strength is permanently degraded. It is interesting to note that, even in the presence of an inert atmosphere, fiber strength is temporarily lowered by the plasma spray process. A fiber strength drop of typically $(100 \times 10^7 \text{ N/m}^2)$ was noted for boron fibers extracted from plasma sprayed tapes, however, as a result of hot pressing the initial fiber strength was fully recovered as measured by tensile testing fibers extracted from the final diffusion bonded composite, Table III.

The above noted intermittent decrease in fiber strength is at present unexplained and has also been noted by other workers who have plasma sprayed boron fiber; however, it does not occur with the plasma spraying of silicon carbide coated boron, BORSIC. In addition, an anomolous increase in boron-aluminum strength has been noted by others (10) which may also relate to a similar mechanism. In this latter work, it was reported that boron aluminum axial composite strength increased during an initial period of annealing of the composite after fabrication. These composites were made through the use of fugitive binder tapes and no plasma spraying was involved in their manufacture.

Composite Fabrication

Composites were fabricated to produce 12 cm x 12 cm rectangular flat panels to optimize fabrication procedures and define the processing envelope of time, temperature and pressure. Both uniaxially reinforced (0°) and multiaxially (0 ± 22) reinforced specimens were fabricated and all specimens were 8 plies thick.

The basic composite fabrication procedure involved the following features:

(a) Pieces of plasma-sprayed tape were cut to size and cleaned of extraneous matter.

(b) Composite layup was made by arranging the cut segments in a stack with the desired orientations. An additional $25 \mu\text{m}$ thick

6061 foil was added to complete the layup and a 25 μm 1100 (unalloyed Al) foil was added to each surface as a protective measure.

(c) If bonding was performed in air, stainless steel foils were placed on the outer layers of the stack to prevent composite surface damage during bonding. If argon was used the stack was placed in a stainless steel bag and pressurized with argon.

(d) The stack of tapes was then placed between preheated platens and the dies immediately brought together and pressure applied. The platen preheat temperature equaled that desired for final hot pressing.

(e) The platens were held closed under pressure for the prescribed hot press time and then separated. The entire composite was then completely removed from the hot press.

(f) The temperature of hot pressing was chosen to remain below the 6061 solidus temperature (582°C). Temperatures between 500 and 565°C were found best.

(g) The time of hot pressing was chosen to be long enough to insure excellent material bonding; however, less than that needed to significantly degrade the boron fiber strength. Total process time of less than 15 minutes were emphasized to maximize efficiency.

(h) Hot-pressing pressure was between 34 and $69 \times 10^6 \text{N/m}^2$.

A typical thermal history of panels fabricated at 550°C is presented in Fig. 4. This was obtained by embedding a thermocouple in the center of a boron-aluminum panel and hot pressing. The time-temperature profiles are given for both five and ten minute process times, where the time refers to that period during which full pressure is applied. This occurs within one minute after insertion of the composite between the preheated hot press platens. The delay time is associated with that period required to accurately position the composite and close the press platens. The thermal profiles reveal that the composite, particularly in the shorter time processing, does not experience the maximum temperature for the entire cycle time. The effective recovery rate of temperature relates to the total hot press system thermal recovery rate and would undoubtedly vary with die plus hot press design. For this reason, it is anticipated that the use of the bonding parameters optimized with the current configuration may require modification for other systems and applications.

Data, shown in Fig. 5, illustrate that hot pressing times of up to 10 minutes at 550°C and up to 40 minutes at 500°C can be used without causing significant fiber degradation. The fiber strengths were obtained by hot pressing monolayer sections of a single plasma sprayed tape and extracting fibers for test. Along with axial composite tensile strength determinations to be described below, these data provide evidence for the ability to hot press at temperatures of as high as 550°C without fiber degradation.

The conditions used to fabricate composite panels from which the data to be described have been obtained, are listed in Table IV.

Uniaxially Reinforced Composite Tensile Test Performance

Tensile test data are presented in Table V. On the basis of axial composite strength and a comparison between as-received and extracted from composite fiber strength, no evidence of fiber degradation was found for any of the specimens fabricated under a diverse range of conditions. In addition, the consistently high values of transverse strength and modulus indicate full consolidation for all specimens. This is reasonable since the lowest temperature used, 500°C, is equal to that commonly utilized in standard slow heat-up-cool-down procedures, and it is anticipated that the benefits of heat-up and cool-down on consolidation are limited compared to the application of pressure at the maximum temperature.

Effect of Cool Down Rate - Because of the fairly rapid cool-down of the composites fabricated, it was possible that the final composite condition could not be considered fully annealed, but instead, heat treated since the 6061 matrix is heat treatable to high strength. To check this possibility, several 90° specimens were annealed at 370°C for 60 minutes and furnace cooled (2010 and 2011). The data indicate only a very small (10 percent) loss in strength and no change in modulus or failure strain indicating that the composites are nearly in the fully annealed condition when fabricated.

Effect of Atmosphere - The comparison made between the use of argon and air (2010 and 2011) indicates no significant difference so that the emphasis was placed on the use of an air atmosphere in the remaining specimens. This relates to the fact that the composite does not reach the highest temperature of bonding until full pressure has been applied for some time. The rapid application of high pressure deforms the plasma sprayed matrix and seals the composite internal structure from the external atmosphere. Otherwise, at the temperatures used, rapid oxidation of the matrix would degrade the composite structure.

Stress-Strain Curves - Both axial and transverse composite tensile stress-strain curves were found to be similar to those obtained in the past for composites diffusion bonded from plasma sprayed tapes, Fig. 6. One noticeable feature of this behavior is low values of transverse composite failure strain. Typical values of between 0.2 to 0.4% strain were common and, for some structural applications, may be considered too low. Attempts were therefore made to raise this level. The principal approach taken was to decrease the amount of plasma spray, relative to foil, in the composite tape and fully consolidated matrix. This was accomplished by plasma spraying for a shorter time than the standard and using either a two mil thick foil or two, one mil thick foils instead of the standard single one mil thick foil per layer. This increase in foil content resulted in composite transverse failure strain values in excess of 0.6% with some values exceeding 1% and a highest value of 1.6%. No loss in transverse strength accompanied this increase, Fig. 7.

Multiaxially Reinforced Composite Fabrication and Tensile Test Performance

The layup sequence for the $0\pm 22^\circ$ composites was used to produce eight layer symmetrical composite panels. The composite fabrication parameters are given in Table VI. In every case, the composite strength parallel to the 0° direction is high with at least one exceptionally high value for each panel. According to previously reported data (5), the 0° strength contribution of the $\pm 22^\circ$ plies is probably on the order of 2.0 to $4.1 \times 10^7 \text{ n/m}^2$ would require extremely high levels of strength by the 0° plies to achieve composite strengths in excess of $1.24 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$. This, however, was the case for half the specimens tested. The composite strength at 90° to the principal fiber axis was approximately equal to or slightly greater than the transverse strength of uniaxially reinforced composites. This was expected since the strength of 68° plies is approximately equal to that of plies oriented at 90° . Composite 2028 exhibited rather low values of transverse strength and probably was not well bonded due to the lower pressure $34 \times 10^6 \text{ N/m}^2$ fabrication. The problem of bonding and densification is magnified for multiaxially reinforced material particularly in an alternating ply layup scheme as used herein because of the inability for fibers to nest as they do in uniaxially oriented material.

Axial Tension-Tension Fatigue

Specimens were fabricated under two sets of conditions for fatigue testing. Those fabricated at 550°C and $6.9 \times 10^7 \text{N/m}^2$ pressure for 5 minutes were found to exhibit signs of delamination along interply boundaries when examined after failure. This type of interply failure was not noted for tensile specimens fabricated under the same conditions and points out that high levels of axial and transverse strength do not necessarily indicate a totally well-bonded composite.

Composite panels 2043, 2079 and 2162 were fabricated at 550°C and $6.9 \times 10^7 \text{N/m}^2$ for 10 minutes and these specimens did not exhibit any signs of interlaminar failure. The average ultimate tensile strengths for composite panels 2043 and 2079 were $1.28 \times 10^9 \text{N/m}^2$ and $1.37 \times 10^9 \text{N/m}^2$ and as would be expected the maximum stresses sustained to 10^7 cycles for these specimens are approximately equal, Fig. (8). The R ratio (or A ratio) was varied for these specimens from $R = 0.1$ ($A=0.82$) to $R = 0.2$ ($A=0.67$) without major effect on the 10^7 cycle limit stress. The R ratio is calculated by dividing the minimum applied stress by the maximum while the A ratio is obtained by dividing the alternating stress (one-half the stress range) by the mean applied stress. This value of the 10^7 limit stress compares favorably with previously reported data for boron reinforced aluminum specimens fabricated by the slow heat-up and cool-down procedure (10-12) and tested using similar A ratios.

The final composite panel tested, 2162, was found to exhibit considerably higher levels of axial tensile strength (average UTS = $1.77 \times 10^9 \text{N/m}^2$) yet the 10^7 cycle run out stress ($1.03 \times 10^9 \text{N/m}^2$) was only slightly higher than that of the previously tested panels. This points to an important factor yet to be explained, which should affect material specifications; high axial tensile strength need not similarly provide improved axial fatigue strength.

Several fatigue specimens which had been tested to 10^7 cycles without failure were retested at higher stress levels to determine whether any coxing effects were observable. The data indicated that no improvement in subsequent high applied stress fatigue could be achieved by pre-fatigue at the lower stress levels.

Flexural Fatigue

Fully reversed cantilever beam fatigue tests were performed on specimens fabricated at 550°C/ $6.9 \times 10^7 \text{N/m}^2$ /10 minutes in air. Failure

occurred at approximately 10^6 cycles for a maximum applied stress (calculated on the basis of deflection) of $1.38 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$. As would be expected, specimen failures occurred just at the edge of the grip region.

Concluding Remarks

The data presented in this paper are part of a larger study (13) which included several additional aspects of composite bonding.

First, because many composite structures will have dimensions exceeding those of the hot press available, a procedure was developed to step press composite panels. Specimens of up to 1.5m in length were step pressed in 7.5 cm increments with excellent results. No fiber degradation or lack of bonding were noted due to the change in procedure required.

Second, all of the composite panels from which the data in this paper were obtained, were flat and of constant cross section thickness. Many anticipated composite applications, however, will not be flat and some, like gas turbine engine fan blades, will be extremely complex in cross section. For this reason, several panels were fabricated with tapered cross sections. These consisted of both uniaxial and multiaxial layups and varied in thickness of from 4 to 10 layers in their cross section. Again, specimens taken from these panels exhibited excellent strength.

Third, the impact of the Quick Bond process on final composite cost was assessed and it was demonstrated that time and labor savings of at least 50% could be obtained. In addition, hot press equipment requirements were substantially reduced. It is these cost savings, combined with automated tape cutting and layup techniques, which permit current projections to indicate that boron aluminum jet engine components can, in the future, be fabricated at costs below those of current production titanium parts.

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References

1. Kreider, K. G. and Leverant, G. R., "Boron Fiber Metal Matrix Composites by Plasma Spraying", USAFML-TR-66-219, July 1966.
2. Kreider, K. G. et al, "Plasma Sprayed Metal Matrix Fiber Reinforced Composites", USAFML-TR-68-119, July 1968.
3. Toth, I. J., "An Exploratory Investigation of the Time Dependent Mechanical Behavior of Composite Materials", USAFML-TR-69-9, April 1969.
4. Menke, G. D., and Toth, I. J., "The Time Dependent Mechanical Behavior of Composite Materials", USAFML-TR-70-174, June 1970.
5. Kreider, K. G. et al, "Metal Matrix Composite Technology", USAFML-TR-71-204, December 1971.
6. Boll, K. G., "Advanced Composite Engine Development Program", USAFML-TR-72-108, July 1972.
7. Scheirer, S. T. and Toth, I. J., "The Mechanical Behavior of Metal Matrix Composites", USAFML-TR-73-178.
8. Brandenburg, G. P., "Production Processes for Composite Tapes", USAFML Contract F-33615-71-C-1646, April 1973.
9. Steinhagen, C. A. et al, "Boron Aluminum Compressor Blades", USAFML Contract F33615-71-C1230, April 1973.
10. Klein, J. J., et al, "Effect of Interfaces in Metal Matrix Composites on Mechanical Properties", AFML-TR-72-226, November 1972.
11. Stuhrke, W. F., AIME Symp. Metal Matrix Comps., Pittsburgh, 1969.
12. Novak, R. C., et al, "Resin Bonded Boron Aluminum", 1972 SAMPE Conference, Los Angeles, Calif.
13. Prewo, K. M., "Exploratory Development on Low Cost Primary Fabrication Processes for Boron Aluminum Composites", USAFML-TR-74-40, November 1973.
14. Kebler, R. W. and Tucker, R. C., "Master Alloy B/Al Tape for Low-Pressure Consolidation", Contract F33615-71-C-1732, Third Quarterly dated April 1972.

Table I Diffusion Bonding of Boron Aluminum

<u>Date</u>	<u>Reference</u>	<u>Tape</u> <u>Type</u>	<u>Diffusion Bonding Conditions</u>			
			<u>Atmo- Sphere</u>	<u>Max. Temperature</u> (°C)	<u>Time At Max. Temp</u> (min)	<u>Pressure</u> (10^6 N/m^2)
1966	1	PS	Argon	400	180	138
1968	2	PS	Argon	400	60	69
1969	3	G	Vacuum	524	60	46
1970	4	G	Vacuum	468	60	46
1971	5	PS	Argon	450-490	30	69
1972	6	PS	Vacuum	510	90	41
1973	7	G	Vacuum	468	60+60	46
1973	8	G	Vacuum	520	30	32
1973	9	G	Vacuum	500	30	34

$$(6.9 \times 10^6 \text{ N/m}^2 = 10^3 \text{ psi})$$

PS = Plasma Sprayed Tape

G = Green (Organic Binder) Tape

Table II Resin Bonded Boron Aluminum Unidirectionally Reinforced

	<u>Boron Aluminum</u>	<u>Boron Epoxy</u>	<u>Resin Bonded</u>
Density (gm/cc)	2.68	2.0	2.40
Short Beam Shear Strength (10^7 N/m ²)	14.5	10.3	8.27
Shear Modulus (10^9 N/m ²)	45.0	7.20	39.0
0° Tensile Strength (10^7 N/m ²)	138.0	138.0	117.0
0° Modulus (10^9 N/m ²)	248.0	220.0	206.0
90° Tensile Strength (10^7 N/m ²)	13.8	8.2	13.8
90° Modulus (10^9 N/m ²)	138.0	22.0	98.5

Table III Fiber Data

<u>Tape</u>	<u>As Received</u>		<u>Extracted From Plasma Sprayed Tape</u>		<u>Extracted From Hot Pressed Composite</u>	
	<u>Avg UTS</u>	<u>STD Dev</u>	<u>Avg UTS</u>	<u>STD Dev</u>	<u>Avg UTS</u>	<u>STD Dev</u>
	(10^7 N/m^2)	(10^7 N/m^2)	(10^7 N/m^2)	(10^7 N/m^2)	(10^7 N/m^2)	(10^7 N/m^2)
1349-1-a	302	±47	201	±16	} 368	±34
-1-b	347	±34	216	±19		
1349-2-a	335	±50	206	±10	} 355	±34
-2-b	354	±31	224	±20		
1349-3-a	333	±26	214	±14	} 367	±34
-3-b	313	±39	202	±20		
1349-4-a	326	±63	210	±14	} 350	±41
-4-b	325	±60	225	±23		

Table IV Composite Fabrication Conditions

<u>Composite Number</u>	<u>Temperature</u> (°C)	<u>Time</u> (min)	<u>Pressure</u> (10^6 N/m ²)	<u>Atmosphere</u>
2010	565	5	69	Air
2011	565	5	69	Argon
2015	550	5	34	Air
2017	550	2	69	Air
2027	550	5	69	Air
2028	550	5	34	Air
2041	550	10	69	Air
2042	550	20	69	Air
2043	550	10	69	Air
2079	550	10	69	Air
2112	550	5	69	Air
2162	550	10	69	Air
2170	550	10	69	Air

Table V Uniaxially Reinforced Composites Tested at 22°C

<u>Composite Number</u>	<u>% Fiber By Volume</u>	Average 0°		Average 90°	
		<u>Tensile Strength</u> (10 ⁷ N/m ²)(Number of Specimens)		<u>Tensile Strength</u> (10 ⁷ N/m ²)(Number of Specimens)	
2010	52	176	(3)	15.8 13.9	(4) (2)*
2011	52	175	(3)	15.2 13.6	(4) (2)*
2014	50	171	(3)	16.8	(3)
2015	50	160	(3)	15.8	(3)
2017	50	151	(3)	17.7	(3)
2111	55	187	(3)	14.6	(4)
2112	55	190	(3)	12.8	(4)
2170	50	182	(3)	19.3	(3)

* Annealed at 370°C for 60 minutes and furnace cooled prior to test.

Table VI 0±22° Reinforced Composites Tested at 22°C

<u>Composite Number</u>	<u>% Fiber by Volume</u>	<u>Average 0° Tensile Strength</u> (10 ⁷ N/m ²)(Number of Specimens)		<u>Average 0° Tensile Strength</u> (10 ⁷ N/m ²)(Number of Specimens)	
2027	54	126	(3)	16.9	(4)
2028	54	123	(3)	10.9	(3)
2041	54	114	(3)	17.2	(4)
2042	54	112	(3)	14.2	(4)

Fig. 1 Boron (145 μm diameter) fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composite diffusion bonded from plasma sprayed tapes.

Fig. 2 Boron (145 μm diameter) fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composite diffusion bonded from preconsolidated tapes.

Fig. 3 Resin bonded boron aluminum composite made from preconsolidated tapes and resin interlayers.

Fig. 4 Thermal history for quick bond process cycles of 5 and 10 minutes at 550°C.

Fig. 5 Axial tensile strength of boron fibers extracted from hot pressed monolayers of plasma sprayed tape.

Fig. 6 Axial and transverse tensile stress-strain curves for uniaxially reinforced boron aluminum.

Fig. 7 Transverse tensile stress-strain curve for uniaxially reinforced boron aluminum. Large value of failure strain obtained by minimizing plasma spray matrix.

Fig. 8 Axial tension-tension fatigue for uniaxially reinforced boron aluminum.